

Formation of Benziminazoles from *o*-Phenylenediamines and Aromatic Aldehydes

N. V. Subba Rao and G. V. Ratnam

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY, OSMANIA UNIVERSITY, HYDERABAD-7,

Benziminazoles may be prepared by a variety of methods which have been very well summarised in an exhaustive review by Wright¹ and in an excellent monograph by Hofmann². In the present article, the formation of benziminazoles from *o*-phenylenediamines and aromatic aldehydes alone is reviewed.

Condensation of o-Phenylenediamine with One Mole of Aromatic Aldehydes

In acidic or alcoholic medium *o*-phenylenediamine condenses with one mole of an aromatic aldehyde resulting in the monoanil³⁻⁸ (I). Depending on the reactivity of the aldehyde, there is a possibility of the formation of dianil (II), only half the diamine being consumed in the reaction⁹. When the condensation is carried out in an oxidising atmosphere, 2-substituted benziminazoles (III) are obtained. Alternately, the monoanils independently prepared may be subjected to oxidative cyclisation to yield the benziminazoles. A wide variety of oxidising agents^{6,7,9-20} have been successfully applied for the preparation of benziminazoles by this method.

Condensation of o-Phenylenediamine with Two Moles of Aromatic Aldehydes

Dianils (II) are obtained in good yields by the condensation of the diamine with two moles of an aldehyde in alcoholic medium^{3,4,8,21-24}, whereas the reaction under acidic conditions leads to the formation of the isomeric 1,2-disubstituted benziminazoles (IV)^{21,22,25-28}.

The condensation of the diamine with a typical aromatic aldehyde has been studied to determine the optimum conditions for the formation of benziminazoles. The addition of reactants in glacial acetic acid at room temperature and working up the products after one hour was found to be the best method. The separation of mono- and disubstituted benziminazoles formed in the reaction could be effected by taking advantage of the fact that the former are preferentially soluble in dilute acetic acid. Several aromatic aldehydes carrying alkyl, alkoxy, hydroxy, halo, nitro, and amino groups were successfully condensed with *o*-phenylenediamine following this method²⁹⁻³¹.

The condensation with aldehydes having hydroxy and amino substituents resulted in the exclusive formation of 1,2-disubstituted benziminazoles (IV) in nearly quantitative yields. Alkyl-, alkoxy-, halo-, and nitro-substituted aldehydes yielded in addition to the disubstituted benziminazoles, varying amounts of mono-substituted compounds (III). Moreover, dianils (II) have been isolated, even under the acidic conditions made use of

in the present experiments, with salicylaldehyde and 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde; these anils could be cyclised to the isomeric disubstituted benziminazoles by heating with acetic acid.

The formation of mono- and disubstituted benziminazoles from the diamine and two moles of aldehydes thus appears to proceed through the intermediate monoanils and dianils respectively, as indicated below. The oxidative cyclisation of the monoanils to the mono-substituted benziminazoles may be taking place by the action of air, as reported by earlier workers^{3,4,32}.

The key intermediate in the condensation seems to be the monoanil (I) which may either undergo oxidative cyclisation resulting in the mono-substituted benziminazole (III) or condense further with another mole of aldehyde, leading to the formation of the di-substituted benziminazole (IV) through the dianil (II). The course of the reaction appears to depend on the nature of the substituent in the aryl group of the monoanil. When the substituent is an electron-releasing group (OH, NMe_2), di-substituted compound is exclusively formed, whereas electron-attracting groups (NO_2 , Cl) give rise to mono-substituted benziminazoles as well.

Condensation of 4-Substituted o-Phenylenediamines with Two Moles of Aromatic Aldehydes

Past literature^{27,33,37} on the condensation of substituted *o*-phenylenediamines with aldehydes is meagre and ambiguous. The condensation of 4-methyl-³⁸, 4-chloro-³⁹ and 4-nitro-⁴⁰ *o*-phenylenediamines with aromatic aldehydes was investigated following the standardised procedure with slight modifications. In general, the results obtained corroborated the conclusions arrived at in the condensations with the simple diamine. This indicates that the substituent in the aldehyde, has a predominating influence on the reaction.

Appreciable amounts of 2-substituted benziminazoles have been isolated in the condensation of the chloro- and nitro-diamines with a number of aldehydes including the hydroxy- and amino-substituted ones, indicating thereby the significant influence exerted by chloro and nitro groups present in the diamine nucleus.

Condensation of the nitrodiamine with aldehydes afforded, in addition to the benziminazoles, mono- and di-anils in a number of cases, thus providing strong support to the stepwise mechanism for the formation of benziminazoles, proposed earlier.

*Isomerism of 1,2-Disubstituted Benziminazoles from 4-Substituted
o-Phenylenediamines*

The dianil (V), formed from one mole of a 4-substituted diamine and two moles of aldehyde on cyclisation gives rise to two isomeric 1,2-disubstituted benziminazoles (VI) and (VII).

Thus arises the problem of fixing the position 5 or 6 of the aromatic substituent in the 1,2-disubstituted benziminazoles from 4-substituted *o*-phenylenediamines and aldehydes. By synthesising the 5- and 6-isomers, (VI) and (VII), adopting unambiguous methods and comparing them with the condensation product (in the case of benzaldehyde), it has been found that the condensation of 4-methyl-*o*-phenylenediamine gives rise to 6-methyl-1,2-disubstituted benziminazoles⁴¹, the 4-chloro-, 5-chloro⁴² and the 4-nitro-diaminer to 6-nitro-⁴³ disubstituted benziminazoles.

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